

Supplementary Fig. 4C

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Control
PI3K δ i

Rabbit monoclonal Anti-Phospho-AKT (Ser473) (D9E)
+ anti-rabbit HRP (ECL)

Mouse monoclonal Anti-AKT (pan) (40D4)
+ anti-mouse IRDye 800 CW

Mouse monoclonal Anti- α -tubulin
+ anti-mouse IRDye 800 CW